

Symbols

Sets

Name	Domains	Description
T	*	Number of hours considered in the optimization
R	*	Selection of the NUTS-2 Region, NL for Netherlands wide
RES	*	Selection of the RES technology
$SCEN$	*	Set with cost data for different scenarios linked to years. 2025 is the base scenario
BAT	*	Selection of the battery storage technology

Parameters

Name	Domains	Description
YR		The number of years that the optimization considers
$CF_{res,t,r}^{Elec}$	RES, T, R	Capacity factor of the energy generation assets, combining onshore, offshore, PV
$OPEX_{res,scen}^{RES}$	$RES, SCEN$	OPEX - Operations and Maintenance cost of generation [EUR2019/MWh] based on Danish Energy Agency (2025)
RES_{res}^{Fixed}	RES	Annualized electricity generation CAPEX [EUR2018/MW*yr]
GRD^{Own}		Grid fees charged on your own produced electricity (10% lower than buy) [EUR/MWh]
GRD^{Buy}		Consuming external electricity via the grid, grid costs (higher than consuming own electricity) [EUR/MWh] based on Adriaansens & Jetten (2021)
BAT_{bat}^{CAPEX}	BAT	Annualized battery CAPEX [EUR2019/yrMW]
ETA^C		Charging efficiency of storage technologies [-] based on Danish Energy Agency (2025)
ETA^{DC}		Discharging efficiency of storage technologies [-] based on Danish Energy Agency (2025)
C_{bat}^{Max}	BAT	C-rate of the different batteries [-]
p^{Max}		Maximum power that can be charged/discharged from the battery [MW]
$SELF^{DC}$		Amount of selfdischarge %/h based on Danish Energy Agency (2025)
RG^C		Regularizer for charging based on the methodology of Han et al. (2024)

RG^{DC}		Regularizer for discharging based on the methodology of Han et al. (2024)
SOC^{Min}		Minimum SOC fraction based on Rangelova & Jones (2025)
SOC^{Max}		Minimum SOC fraction based on Rangelova & Jones (2025)
C^{Elyzr}		Capacity of the electrolysis plant [MW]
CF^{Lo}		Lower capacity bound on the capacity factor, where there is no syngas production [-]
A^{Elyzr}		Slope of the syngas production curve as a function of the capacity factor [cf/(kg*MW)] based on post processing of sub-model
B^{Elyzr}		Intercept of the syngas production curve as a function of the capacity factor [kg/MW] based on post processing of sub-model
$ELEC_t^{Price}$	*	Market selling price of electricity [EUR/MWh] based on ENTSO-E (2025)
GE^{Cons}		Percentage per hour that can be consumed as grid electricity [%]
ST^{MaxL}		Maximum loading and unloading capacity [tonne/h]
ST^{Max}		Maximum storage mass of the tank [tonnes]
CPM^{SG}		Heat capacity syngas (2 H ₂ : 1 CO) [J/(kg*K)]
D^t		Temperature difference input 220 °C output 12 °C [K]
CRF^{Sto}		CRF of the storage 30 year 8% [-]
$CAPEX^{Heater}$		The CAPEX in EUR/kW for the electric gas heater based on data from Agora Energiewende (2022) [EUR2019/kW]
$CAPEX^{Cooler}$		The CAPEX in EUR/kW for the electric gas cooler based on data from Fraunhofer IEG (2024) [EUR2019/kW]
COP^{Cooler}		The COP for cooling down the gas stream to 12 °C using a compression cooler from Fraunhofer IEG (2024) [-]
COP^{Heater}		The COP for (pre-)heating the gas stream to 220 °C using an electric heater from Agora Energiewende (2022) [-]
$SG^{Storage}$		Total storage cost factor based on Bulk storage of hydrogen [EUR2019/t] based on Papadias & Ahluwalia (2021)
SG^{Prod}		Scenario input, scalar regarding the annual syngas supplied to a SAF plant [ktonne/yr]

Variables

Name	Domains	Description
c_{res}^{RES}	*	Power capacity of the renewable energy generation [MW]
$gen_{res,t}^{In}$	*, *	Energy generated by the renewable energy generation [MWh]
$cost^{Gen}$		Cost for generating electricity (annualized, CAPEX and OPEX) [EUR2019/yr]
e_t^{Elyzr}	*	Energy that is directly used in the electrolysis plant [MWh]
e_t^{Curt}	*	Energy that needs to be curtailed or that is not used at all [MWh]
e_t^{Bat}	*	Energy that is stored in the battery [MWh]
e_t^H	*	Energy that needs to be used for heating the stored syngas to 220 °C [MWh]
e_t^C	*	Energy that needs to be used for cooling syngas to 12 °C for storage [MWh]
$u_{bat,t}$	BAT, T	Indicator for charging mode 0= discharging, 1= charging (u in [0,1])
c_{bat}^{Bat}	*	Overall yearly installed capacity of the battery [MW]
$p_{bat,t}^C$	BAT, T	Charging power [MW]
$p_{bat,t}^{DC}$	BAT, T	Discharging power [MW]
$e_{bat,t}^{SOC}$	BAT, T	State of charge in the battery/ Available energy [MWh]
$e_{bat,t}^{Net}$	BAT, T	Net charged/discharged energy from the battery [MWh]
reg_{bat}^{Bat}	BAT	Regulizer variable for the storage cost, where charging and discharging simultaneously are discouraged
$cost^{RegBat}$		Total regulated cost of the battery
$cost_{bat}^{Bat}$	BAT	The actual battery storage costs without regulizers
cf_t^{Elyzr}	*	Capacity factor of the electrolysis plant during an hour [-]
m_t^{SG}	*	Variable for the syngas that is produced in each hour [tonne]
e_t^{Grid}	*	Electricity used from the grid [MWh]
e_t^{Input}	*	Electricity input into the electrolysis plant [MWh]
$e_{bat,t}^{DC_Elyzr}$	*, *	Electricity received in the electrolysis plant from discharging the battery [MWh]
$e_{bat,t}^{DC_Sell}$	*, *	Electricity discharged from the battery that is sold on the electricity market [MWh]
$e_{bat,t}^{DC_C}$	*, *	Electricity discharged from the battery that is used for pre-heating the syngas for FT synthesis [MWh]

$e_{bat,t}^{DC_H}$	*, *	Electricity discharged from the battery that is used for cooling down the syngas for storage [MWh]
$cost_t^{Grid}$	*	Variable for cost of consuming electricity from the grid total [EUR2019]
$cost^{GridTot}$		Cost of consuming grid electricity averaged over the years of the optimization [EUR2019/yr]
l_t^{St1}		Indicator for loading and unloading 1 = loading, 0 = unloading (1 in [0,1])
m_t^{FT}	*	Amount of syngas delivered to the FT synthesis facility [t/h]
m_t^L	*	Amount of syngas that is loaded in that operating hour [t/h]
m_t^{Un}	*	Amount of syngas that is unloaded in that operating hour [t/h]
c^{Sto}		Size in tonne of syngas storage [tonne]
sg_t^{St}	T	Mass of syngas stored in the storage system [tonnes]
$sg_t^{Cycling}$	*	Net amount of syngas that is stored or delivered in the operating hour [t/h]
q_t^L	*	Energy required for loading syngas [kW]
q_t^{Un}	*	Energy required for unloading syngas [kW]
q^{CapC}		Capacity of the cooler for loading syngas [kW]
q^{CapH}		Capacity of the heater for unloading syngas [kW]
$cost^{StoH}$		Storage heating cost [EUR2019/yr]
$cost^{StoC}$		Storage cooling cost [EUR2019/yr]
$cost^{StoHC}$		Cost for heating and cooling syngas to make it suitable for storage [EUR2019/yr]
$cost^{Sto}$		Cost of storing syngas in a storage system [EUR2019/yr]
m_t^{Tot}	*	Total flow of syngas entering the FT synthesis plant [tonne/h]
z^{St1}		Cost - objective variable given a target of the total amount of syngas produced [EUR2019/yr]
rev_t^{Elec}	*	Total revenue of selling electricity [EUR2019]
rev^{Sell}		Revenue of selling electricity per year [EUR2019/yr]
z^{St2}		Net cost - objective variable of the second stage given a target of the total amount of syngas produced and revenue sold [EUR2019/yr]
l_t^{St2}	*	Binary for loading and unloading 1 = loading, 0 = unloading (1 in [0,1])

$u_{bat,t}^{St2}$, *	Binary for charging mode 0= discharging, 1= charging (u in [0,1])
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Equations

Name	Domains	Description
$eqGenRES_{res,t}$, *	The production of electricity per technology and timestep
$eqGenCost$		The electricity generation costs
$eqEleUse_t$	*	The use of the generated electricity, charging, using in the electrolysis plant, curtailing, heating, cooling for storage, and selling to the grid for the grid electricity price [MWh]
$eqChargeInput_t$	*	Energy input into the battery systems
$eqChargpUp_{bat,t}$, *	Charging power upper bound
$eqDChargUp_{bat,t}$, *	Discharging power upper bound
$eqEnergyNet_{bat,t}$, *	Net hourly energy absorbed or injected energy in the battery
$eqEnergyBal_{bat,t}$, *	Energy balance of the battery - Energy stored in the battery
$eqBatTight_{bat,t}$, *	Tight formulation of the charging power and state of charge
$eqBatTightDC_{bat,t}$, *	Tight formulation of the charging power and state of charge
$eqChargePowerLimit_{bat,t}$	BAT, T	Charging power limit based on variable capacity
$leqDischargePowerLimit_{bat,t}$	BAT, T	Discharging power limit based on variable capacity
$eqEnergyAdeq_{bat,t}$, *	Tight formulation to ensure there is enough energy to discharge from the battery
$eqDCTight_{bat,t}$, *	Tight formulation to ensure the discharge is smaller than the max charge capacity in a certain hour
$eqBat_{bat,t}^{MinC}$, *	Minimum SOC of the battery
$eqBat_{bat,t}^{MaxC}$, *	Maximum SOC of the battery
$eqRegBatCost_{at}$	*	The regularized battery storage costs

$eqTotBatCost$		The total battery cost, summing different types of batteries (currently only Li-ion 4h)
$eqBatCost2_{bat}$	*	Calculates the actual battery storage costs without regularizers
$eqDC_{bat,t}^{Bat}$	*, *	The power discharged in each hour (energy), that is used for different applications within the plant
$eqElyzr_t^{In}$	*	Energy that is used by the electrolyzer from direct use, grid electricity, and the battery
$eqElyzrCF_t$	*	Link the energy generation of the renewables to the capacity factor of the electrolysis plant
$eqProduction_t$	*	Equation with the production amounts of syngas as a function of the capacity factor and the input capacity of the electrolysis plant
$eqGrid_t^{Limit}$	*	Maximum percentage of grid electricity used in each hour
$eqGrid_t^{Cost}$	*	The cost of consuming electricity from the grid
$eqTot^{GridCost}$		Cost of consuming grid electricity averaged over the years of the optimization
$eqSGSupply_t$	*	The syngas supply to the FT and the syngas storage from the electrolysis plant
$eqLMin_t$	*	Minimum loading of the syngas storage system
$eqLMax_t$	*	Maximum loading of the syngas storage system
$eqLup_t$	*	Upper bound unloading
$eqUnup_t$	*	Discharging power upper bound
$eqCycleSG_t$	*	Net hourly absorbed or injected syngas to the storage system
$eqStSG_t$	*	Storage balance
$eqCyclicSto_t$	*	Cyclic constraint on the storage mass
$eqSto_t^{MinC}$	*	Minimum amount of syngas in the storage system
$eqSto_t^{MaxC}$	*	Maximum amount of syngas in the storage system
eqQ_t^L	*	Equation for the energy required for loading

		the syngas into the storage system due to cooling requirements
eqQ_t^{Un}	*	Equation for the energy required for unloading syngas from the storage system due to pre-heating to FT conditions
eqQ_t^{CapL}	*	Cooling capacity needed for loading syngas into the storage system
eqQ_t^{CapUn}	*	Heating capacity needed for loading syngas into the storage system
$eqSTO^C$		Annualized CAPEX for investing into the cooler
$eqSTO^H$		Annualized CAPEX for investing into the heater
$eqStoElecH_t$	*	Electricity requirement for operating the heater
$eqStoElecC_t$	*	Electricity requirement for operating the gas cooler
$eqTotHC$		Calculating the total storage heating and cooling cost
$eqCostStoSG$		The syngas storage cost, using the same regularized approach as for the battery
$eqSGFT_t$	*	Calculates the total flow of syngas entering the FT synthesis plant
$eqSG$		Syngas input into the SAF plant across the modeling horizon
$eqUpCF$		Upper capacity factor of the syngas electrolysis plant
$eqObj$		Objective function of the first stage objective, regarding the minimization of costs
$eqSellCurt_t$	*	Equation for selling in the second stage, the curtailed electricity in the first stage, while re-optimizing the operation
$eqTotSellRev$		Total revenue from selling electricity
$eqObj2$		Second stage objective
$eqLup2_t$	*	Charging power upper bound
$eqUnup2_t$	*	Discharging power upper bound

eqChargpup2 _{bat,t}	, *	Charging power upper bound
eqDChargplup2 _{bat,t}	, *	Discharging power upper bound

Naming conventions

Throughout the mathematical formulation, variables are represented in lowercase italics, and parameters are capitalized in italics. The domain of a variable is displayed in lowercase italic subscript, while the roman superscript provides additional details about the symbols used in the model. The sets after for all are written capitalized.

Equation Definitions

$$\text{eqGenRES}_{res,t} \quad gen_{res,t}^{In} = \sum_r (CF_{res,t,r}^{Elec} \cdot c_{res}^{RES}) \quad \forall RES, T \quad (1)$$

$$\text{eqGenCost} \quad cost^{Gen} = \sum_{res} (c_{res}^{RES} \cdot RES_{res}^{Fixed} \cdot 1000) + \frac{\sum_{res,t} (gen_{res,t}^{In} \cdot \sum_{scen} OPEX_{res,scen}^{RES}) + \sum_{res,t} (gen_{res,t}^{In} \cdot GRD^{Own})}{YR} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{eqEleUse}_t \quad \sum_{res} gen_{res,t}^{In} = e_t^{Elyzr} + e_t^{Curt} + e_t^{Bat} + e_t^H + e_t^C \quad \forall T \quad (3)$$

$$\text{eqChargeInput}_t \quad e_t^{Bat} = \sum_{bat} p_{bat,t}^C \quad \forall T \quad (4)$$

$$\text{eqChargpUp}_{bat,t} \quad p_{bat,t}^C \leq C_{bat}^{Max} \cdot p^{Max} \cdot u_{bat,t} \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (5)$$

$$\text{eqDChargUp}_{bat,t} \quad p_{bat,t}^{DC} \leq C_{bat}^{Max} \cdot p^{Max} \cdot (1 - u_{bat,t}) \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (6)$$

$$\text{eqEnergyNet}_{bat,t} \quad e_{bat,t}^{Net} = ETA^C \cdot p_{bat,t}^C - \frac{p_{bat,t}^{DC}}{ETA^{DC}} \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (7)$$

$$\text{eqEnergyBal}_{bat,t} \quad e_{bat,t--1}^{SOC} \cdot (1 - SELF^{DC}) + e_{bat,t}^{Net} = e_{bat,t}^{SOC} \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{eqBatTight}_{bat,t} \quad p_{bat,t}^C \leq \frac{P^{Max} \cdot C_{bat}^{Max}}{ETAC} \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{eqBatTightDC}_{bat,t} \quad p_{bat,t}^{DC} \leq (P^{Max} \cdot C_{bat}^{Max} - e_{bat,t-1}^{SOC}) \cdot ETA^{DC} \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{eqChargePowerLimit}_{bat,t} \quad p_{bat,t}^C \leq \frac{C_{bat}^{max}}{ETAC} \cdot c_{bat}^{Bat} \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{eqDischargePowerLimit}_{bat,t} \quad p_{bat,t}^{DC} \leq C_{bat}^{Max} \cdot c_{bat}^{Bat} \cdot ETA^{DC} \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{eqEnergyAdeq}_{bat,t} \quad p_{bat,t}^{DC} \leq e_{bat,t-1}^{SOC} \cdot ETA^{DC} \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{eqDCTight}_{bat,t} \quad p_{bat,t}^{DC} \leq P^{Max} - p_{bat,t}^C \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{eqBat}^{MinC}_{bat,t} \quad e_{bat,t}^{SOC} \leq c_{bat}^{Bat} \cdot SOC^{Max} \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{eqBat}^{MaxC}_{bat,t} \quad e_{bat,t}^{SOC} \geq c_{bat}^{Bat} \cdot SOC^{Min} \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbf{eqRegBatCost}_{bat} \quad reg_{bat}^{Bat} = c_{bat}^{Bat} \cdot BAT_{bat}^{CAPEX} + \sum_t (RG^C \cdot p_{bat,t}^C + RG^{DC} \cdot p_{bat,t}^{DC}) \quad \forall BAT \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{eqTotBatCost} \quad cost^{RegBat} = \sum_{bat} reg_{bat}^{Bat} \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{eqBatCost2}_{bat} \quad cost_{bat}^{Bat} = c_{bat}^{Bat} \cdot BAT_{bat}^{CAPEX} \quad \forall BAT \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{eqDC}_{bat,t}^{Bat} \quad p_{bat,t}^{DC} = e_{bat,t}^{DC,Sell} + e_{bat,t}^{DC,Elyzr} + e_{bat,t}^{DC,H} + e_{bat,t}^{DC,H} \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{eqElyzr}_t^{In} \quad e_t^{Elyzr} + \sum_{bat} e_{bat,t}^{DC,Elyzr} + e_t^{Grid} = e_t^{Input} \quad \forall T \quad (21)$$

$$\mathbf{eqElyzrCF}_t \quad e_t^{Input} = c_f^{Elyzr} \cdot C^{Elyzr} \quad \forall T \quad (22)$$

$$\mathbf{eqProduction}_t \quad m_t^{SG} = \frac{C^{Elyzr} \cdot (A^{Elyzr} \cdot c_f^{Elyzr} \cdot 100 - B^{Elyzr})}{1000} \quad \forall T \quad (23)$$

$$\mathbf{eqGrid}_t^{Limit} \quad e_t^{Grid} \leq \frac{GE^{Cons}}{100} \cdot e_t^{Input} \quad \forall T \quad (24)$$

$$\mathbf{eqGrid}_t^{Cost} \quad e_t^{Grid} \cdot ELEC_t^{Price} + e_t^{Grid} \cdot GRD^{Buy} = cost_t^{Grid} \quad \forall T \quad (25)$$

$$\mathbf{eqTot}_{GridCost} \quad \frac{\sum_t cost_t^{Grid}}{YR} = cost^{GridTot} \quad (26)$$

$$\mathbf{eqSGSupply}_t \quad m_t^{SG} = m_t^{FT} + m_t^L \quad \forall T \quad (27)$$

$$\mathbf{eqLMin}_t \quad -ST^{MaxL} \leq sg_t^{Cycling} \quad \forall T \quad (28)$$

$$\mathbf{eqLMax}_t \quad sg_t^{Cycling} \leq ST^{MaxL} \quad \forall T \quad (29)$$

$$\mathbf{eqLup}_t \quad m_t^L \leq ST^{Max} \cdot ST^{MaxL} \cdot l_t \quad \forall T \quad (30)$$

$$\text{eqUnup}_t \quad m_t^{\text{Un}} \leq ST^{\text{Max}} \cdot ST^{\text{MaxL}} \cdot (1 - l_t) \quad \forall T \quad (31)$$

$$\text{eqCycleSG}_t \quad sg_t^{\text{Cycling}} = m_t^{\text{L}} - m_t^{\text{Un}} \quad \forall T \quad (32)$$

$$\text{eqStSG}_t \quad sg_{t-1}^{\text{St}} + sg_t^{\text{Cycling}} = sg_t^{\text{St}} \quad \forall T \quad (33)$$

$$\text{eqCyclicSto}_t \quad sg_{t=0}^{\text{Cycling}} = sg_{t=n}^{\text{Cycling}} \quad \forall T \quad (34)$$

$$\text{eqSto}_t^{\text{MinC}} \quad sg_t^{\text{St}} \leq c^{\text{Sto}} \cdot SOC^{\text{Max}} \quad \forall T \quad (35)$$

$$\text{eqSto}_t^{\text{MaxC}} \quad sg_t^{\text{St}} \geq c^{\text{Sto}} \cdot SOC^{\text{Min}} \quad \forall T \quad (36)$$

$$\text{eqQ}_t^{\text{L}} \quad q_t^{\text{L}} = \frac{m_t^{\text{L}} \cdot CPM^{\text{SG}} \cdot D^t}{3600} \quad \forall T \quad (37)$$

$$\text{eqQ}_t^{\text{Un}} \quad q_t^{\text{Un}} = \frac{m_t^{\text{Un}} \cdot CPM^{\text{SG}} \cdot D^t}{3600} \quad \forall T \quad (38)$$

$$\text{eqQ}_t^{\text{CapL}} \quad q^{\text{CapC}} \geq q_t^{\text{L}} \quad \forall T \quad (39)$$

$$\text{eqQ}_t^{\text{CapUn}} \quad q^{\text{CapH}} \geq q_t^{\text{Un}} \quad \forall T \quad (40)$$

$$\text{eqSTO}^{\text{C}} \quad q^{\text{CapC}} \cdot CAPEX^{\text{Cooler}} \cdot CRF^{\text{Sto}} = cost^{\text{StoH}} \quad (41)$$

$$\mathbf{eqSto}^H \quad q^{\text{CapH}} \cdot CAPEX^{\text{Heater}} \cdot CRF^{\text{Sto}} = \text{cost}^{\text{StoC}} \quad (42)$$

$$\mathbf{eqStoElecH}_t \quad \frac{q_t^{\text{Un}}}{COP^{\text{Heater}}} = \sum_{\text{bat}} e_{\text{bat},t}^{\text{DC,h}} + e_t^{\text{H}} \quad \forall T \quad (43)$$

$$\mathbf{eqStoElecC}_t \quad \frac{q_t^{\text{L}}}{COP^{\text{Cooler}}} = \sum_{\text{bat}} e_{\text{bat},t}^{\text{DC,c}} + e_t^{\text{C}} \quad \forall T \quad (44)$$

$$\mathbf{eqTotHC} \quad \text{cost}^{\text{StoHC}} = \text{cost}^{\text{StoH}} + \text{cost}^{\text{StoC}} \quad (45)$$

$$\mathbf{eqCostStoSG} \quad \text{cost}^{\text{StoReg}} = c^{\text{Sto}} \cdot SG^{\text{Storage}} + \text{cost}^{\text{StoHC}} + \sum_t (RG^{\text{C}} \cdot q_t^{\text{L}} + RG^{\text{DC}} \cdot q_t^{\text{Un}}) \quad (46)$$

$$\mathbf{eqSGFT}_t \quad m_t^{\text{Tot}} = m_t^{\text{FT}} + m_t^{\text{Un}} \quad \forall T \quad (47)$$

$$\mathbf{eqSG} \quad SG^{\text{Prod}} \cdot YR = \sum_t \left(\frac{m_t^{\text{Tot}}}{1000} \right) \quad (48)$$

$$\mathbf{eqUpCF} \quad \sum_t c f_t^{\text{Elyzr}} \leq 8000 \cdot YR + 760 \cdot YR \cdot CF^{\text{Lo}} \quad (49)$$

$$\mathbf{eqObj} \quad \text{cost}^{\text{Gen}} + \text{cost}^{\text{RegBat}} + \text{cost}^{\text{Sto}} + \text{Cost}^{\text{GridTot}} = z^{\text{St1}} \quad (50)$$

$$\mathbf{eqSellCurt}_t \quad (e_t^{\text{Curt}} + \sum_{\text{bat}} e_{\text{bat},t}^{\text{DC,sell}}) \cdot ELEC_t^{\text{Price}} = \text{rev}_t^{\text{Elec}} \quad \forall T \quad (51)$$

$$\mathbf{eqTotSellRev} \quad \frac{\sum_t \text{rev}_t^{\text{Elec}}}{YR} = \text{rev}^{\text{Sell}} \quad (52)$$

$$\mathbf{eqObj2} \quad z^{St1} - rev^{Sell} = z^{St2} \quad (53)$$

$$\mathbf{eqLup2}_t \quad m_t^L \leq ST^{Max} \cdot ST^{MaxL} \quad \forall T \quad (54)$$

$$\mathbf{eqUnup2}_t \quad m_t^{Un} \leq ST^{Max} \cdot ST^{MaxL} \cdot (1 - I_t^{St2}) \quad \forall T \quad (55)$$

$$\mathbf{eqChargpup2}_{bat,t} \quad p_{bat,t}^C \leq C_{bat}^{Max} \cdot P^{Max} \cdot u_{bat,t}^{St2} \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (56)$$

$$\mathbf{eqDChargplup2}_{bat,t} \quad p_{bat,t}^{DC} \leq C_{bat}^{Max} \cdot P^{Max} \cdot (1 - u_{bat,t}^{St2}) \quad \forall BAT, T \quad (57)$$

$$gen^{In}_{*,*} \geq 0 \quad \forall *,*$$

$$c_*^{Res} \geq 0 \quad \forall *$$

$$cost^{Gen} \geq 0 \quad \forall$$

$$e_*^{Elyzr} \geq 0 \quad \forall *$$

$$e_*^{Curt} \geq 0 \quad \forall *$$

$$e_*^{Bat} \geq 0 \quad \forall *$$

$$e_*^H \geq 0 \quad \forall *$$

$$e_*^C \geq 0 \quad \forall *$$

$$p_{bat,t}^{Bat} \geq 0 \quad \forall BAT, T$$

$$p_{bat,t}^{DC} \geq 0 \quad \forall BAT, T$$

$$e_{bat,t}^{SOC} \geq 0 \quad \forall BAT, T$$

$$c_*^{Bat} \geq 0 \quad \forall *$$

$$reg_{bat}^{Bat} \geq 0 \quad \forall BAT$$

$$cost^{RegBat} \geq 0 \quad \forall$$

$$cost_{bat}^{Bat} \geq 0 \quad \forall BAT$$

$$e_{*,*}^{DC_Sell} \geq 0 \quad \forall *,*$$

$$e_{*,*}^{DC_Elyzr} \geq 0 \quad \forall *,*$$

$$e_{*,*}^{DC_H} \geq 0 \quad \forall *,*$$

$$e_{*,*}^{DC_C} \geq 0 \quad \forall *,*$$

$$e_*^{Grid} \geq 0 \quad \forall *$$

$$e_*^{Input} \geq 0 \quad \forall *$$

$$cf_*^{Elyzr} \geq 0 \quad \forall *$$

$$m_*^{SG} \geq 0 \quad \forall *$$

$$\begin{aligned}
m_*^{FT} &\geq 0 \quad \forall * \\
m_*^L &\geq 0 \quad \forall * \\
m_*^{Un} &\geq 0 \quad \forall * \\
sg_t^{St} &\geq 0 \quad \forall T \\
c^{Sto} &\geq 0 \quad \forall \\
q_*^l &\geq 0 \quad \forall * \\
q_*^{Un} &\geq 0 \quad \forall * \\
q^{CapC} &\geq 0 \quad \forall \\
q^{CapH} &\geq 0 \quad \forall \\
cost^{StoH} &\geq 0 \quad \forall \\
cost^{StoC} &\geq 0 \quad \forall \\
cost^{StoHC} &\geq 0 \quad \forall \\
cost^{Sto} &\geq 0 \quad \forall \\
m_*^{Tot} &\geq 0 \quad \forall * \\
l_*^{St2} &\in 0,1 \quad \forall * \\
u_{*,*}^{St2} &\in 0,1 \quad \forall *,*
\end{aligned}$$

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